

1 Model uncertainty obscures major driver of soil carbon

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15 Understanding the formation and stabilization mechanisms of soil organic carbon
16 (SOC) is important for managing land carbon (C) and mitigating climate change. Tao et
17 al.¹ reported that microbial C use efficiency (CUE) is the primary determinant of global
18 SOC storage and that the relative impact of plant C inputs on SOC is minor. While soil
19 microbes undoubtedly play an important role in SOC cycling, we are concerned about
20 the robustness of the approach taken by Tao et al.¹ The potential biases in their
21 analyses may lead to misleading, model-dependent results.

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23 An important piece of evidence in support of an empirical relationship between
24 CUE and SOC stems from a meta-analysis based on 132 paired CUE and SOC

25 measurements. Tao and colleagues¹ applied a linear mixed effect model to this dataset
26 that included CUE, mean annual temperature (MAT), soil depth, and random effects,
27 and explained 55% of the variation in the log-transformed SOC (Fig. 2a and Extended
28 Data Table 1 in Tao et al.¹). In their linear mixed effect model, C inputs to soil were not
29 included despite the authors acknowledging past empirical and theoretical evidence for
30 a major role. To demonstrate that C inputs can also drive SOC variation in their dataset,
31 we extracted net primary production (NPP) from the globally gridded MODIS² for each
32 soil sampling location and used it as a first-order proxy for soil C inputs following ref. ¹.
33 By replacing CUE with NPP in the authors' linear mixed effect model, we explained a
34 larger proportion of the variation in SOC – namely, 71% with NPP compared to 55%
35 with CUE (Table 1 in the present manuscript). This finding suggests that the empirical
36 results of Tao et al.¹ may not be robust to the inclusion of other variables, and raises
37 questions about the importance of CUE in explaining SOC variations.

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39 Tao et al. (2023) further present results from a parameter sensitivity analysis of a
40 process-oriented model which showcase a causal and dominant relationship between
41 CUE and SOC (Fig. 4 in Tao et al., 2023). In order to address uncertainties in model
42 structure and parameters that hamper robust model predictions, the authors used a
43 comprehensive model-data assimilation approach to calibrate a selection of 23
44 parameters of a SOC model based on a global dataset of SOC measurements. The
45 calibrated SOC model was then used to quantify the sensitivity of SOC predictions to a
46 selection of potential drivers of SOC, i.e., by varying their values around the optimal or
47 prescribed values one-by-one. We argue that the omission of C inputs and a microbial

48 parameter shown to critically affect the sensitivity of SOC to changes in C inputs in
49 microbial explicit SOC models in the set of optimized parameters raises doubts about
50 the robustness of the findings of the sensitivity analysis.

51
52 First, Tao et al. (2023) assumed a model structure which may inherently
53 predispose their analyses to suggest a low importance of C inputs on steady-state SOC.
54 In particular, the chosen model represents the rate of microbial turnover as a linear
55 function of microbial biomass (i.e., 'density-independent' with exponent $\beta=1$, unless
56 otherwise specified, β refers to the exponent of microbial turnover rate in this study) as
57 opposed to a potential super-linear function (i.e., 'density-dependent' with $\beta>1$) as
58 suggested in past studies³⁻⁵. Without this density-dependent microbial turnover, a given
59 change in C inputs may result in a proportional change in the microbial biomass pool
60 and a consequent insensitivity of the SOC pool. This type of model is inconsistent with
61 multiple empirical and theoretical results which show that steady-state SOC pools are
62 sensitive to changes in C inputs, and that this can be better simulated using SOC
63 models with density-dependent microbial turnover³. Figure 1 in the present manuscript
64 shows that a switch from density-independent ($\beta=1$) to density-dependent ($\beta>1$)
65 microbial turnover greatly increases the impact of C input to SOC in the Microbial-
66 Mineral Carbon Stabilization (MIMICS) model⁶ (Fig. 1a–c) and in the Millennial model⁴
67 (Fig.1d–f).

68
69 While Tao et al. explored the potential need for a sub-linear exponent on the rate
70 of enzyme production – i.e., enzyme production \sim (microbial biomass) ^{β_{enz}} where $0 <$

71 $\beta_{enz} < 1$ – in their SOC model (here ' β_{enz} ' is used to distinguish it from the exponent β),
72 this modification is functionally and theoretically distinct from the density-dependent
73 microbial turnover with $\beta > 1$ proposed in earlier work³. We conducted a sensitivity
74 analysis⁷ to determine whether SOC behaved the same if an exponent was assigned to
75 enzyme production ($0 < \beta_{enz} < 1$ as in¹) versus microbial turnover ($1 < \beta < 2$ as in³). We
76 found that the sensitivity of SOC to a variation of +/-10% of CUE is equal to 1.3 when β
77 and β_{enz} are both equal to 1, but is much less when the exponents are not equal to 1:
78 0.48 and 0.73 for a 50% change in β_{enz} and β on turnover, respectively. On the other
79 hand, the sensitivity of SOC to a variation of +/-10% of C input is equal to 0 when β and
80 $\beta_{enz} = 1$, 0.52 when β_{enz} is modified by 50%, and 0.34 when β on turnover is modified by
81 50%. This indicates that the results of Tao et al. are very contingent on the assumed
82 model structure. If β associated with turnover is not found with observations to be
83 mostly 1 (as for enzyme production), then a lower sensitivity of SOC to CUE and a
84 greater sensitivity of SOC to C input may have been observed. Besides, the exploration
85 of the exponent β_{enz} by Tao et al. are only in the reply to the reviewers and there is not a
86 sufficient description of how the results were obtained.

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88 Second, Tao et al. approximated C inputs to the soil using net primary production
89 (NPP) from predictions of a land surface model. NPP is a notoriously uncertain C flux
90 and it is not clear to what extent NPP from land surface models actually reflects C
91 inputs to soil and its spatial variations⁸. The use of the interannual variation in NPP from
92 a single land surface model to characterize uncertainty in C inputs, as done in the
93 optimization in this study, falls arguably short to characterize the true uncertainty. Its

94 implications for the outcome of the study remains elusive, representing a source of
95 uncertainty. The inclusion of C input⁹ as a parameter for optimization at the site scale
96 rather than the inclusion of NPP as an environmental driver for the global extrapolation¹
97 of site-specific optimized parameters could be a way forward.

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99 In summary, we highlight several statistical and process-based model assumptions
100 that may have biased the overarching conclusion that CUE is the dominant control on
101 spatial variation of SOC. We argue that changes in soil microbial CUE itself are
102 influenced by environmental factors, including C inputs as well as the quality of litter
103 ^{10,11}. Tao et al.'s findings contradict numerous empirical studies that report that changes
104 in plant inputs significantly alter SOC (e.g., in ¹²⁻¹⁴). We believe that further examination
105 of statistical and process-based model structures is needed to demonstrate the
106 robustness of the conclusions presented. Moreover, future research efforts should be
107 allocated towards investigating multiple mechanisms of SOC stabilization and loss,
108 rather than solely focusing on CUE.

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111 **Table 1 Net primary productivity may explain more variation in soil organic**
112 **carbon storage (SOC) than microbial carbon-use efficiency (CUE).** We performed
113 the same mixed-model regression analyses as in Tao et al., but also explored the
114 importance of net primary production (NPP; g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) as a first-order proxy for C
115 inputs to the soil. In both the present study and in Tao et al. (2023), the linear mixed
116 effect model also includes mean annual temperature (MAT; °Celsius) and soil depth

117 (cm), and the study sources were added as the random effects. To ensure the
 118 comparability of coefficients across all three explanatory variables (i.e., NPP, MAT, and
 119 depth) in the results, we applied standardization using the Z-score method, which
 120 maintains the explanatory power of the model. *CI* and *p* indicate 95% confidence
 121 interval and statistical significance, respectively.

<i>Predictors</i>	log₁₀(SOC)		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	1.37	1.24 – 1.50	< 0.001
NPP	0.25	0.19 – 0.32	< 0.001
MAT	-0.10	-0.16 – -0.04	0.002
Depth	-0.14	-0.19 – -0.09	< 0.001
Random Effects			
σ^2	0.05		
$\tau_{00 \text{ Source}}$	0.05		
ICC	0.50		
N_{Source}	15		
Observations	121		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.417 / 0.709		

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126 **Fig. 1 Sensitivity of the CUE-SOC relationship to the inclusion of density-**

127 **dependent microbial turnover in process-based soil models.** Predicted soil organic

128 carbon (SOC) stocks at steady-state from the MIMICS (a-c) and Millennial (d-f)

129 microbial-explicit SOC models using a range of density-dependent microbial turnover

130 exponent (β) values, net primary productivity (NPP), and microbial carbon use efficiency

131 (CUE). Simulations for a mean annual temperature of 20°Celsius, soil clay content of
 132 20%, and litter lignin to nitrogen ratio of 10. The SOC values in each plot were
 133 standardized using the Z-score method to ensure comparability.

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143 **Competing interests:**

144 The authors declare no competing interests.

145 **Contributions:**

146 DSG, XH and EA conceptualized and designed this idea. XH, RA, EA, KG, HZ, and
147 DSG discussed the results and contributed to the text.

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150 **Reference:**

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